

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
BLOOD BANK AND DONOR MANAGEMENT SYSTEM
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

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INTRODUCTION

1.1:-Project Definition:

The **BLOODBANK & DONOR MANAGEMENT SYSTEM** is great project. this project is designed for successful completion of project on blood bank management system. the basic building aim is to provide blood donation service to the city recently. **BloodBank& Donor Management System** is a browser based system that is designed to store, process, retrieve and analyze information concerned with the administrative and inventory management within a blood bank. This project aims at maintaining all the information pertaining to blood donors, different blood groups available in each blood bank and help them manage in a better way. Aim is to provide transparency in this field, make the process of obtaining blood from a blood bank hassle free and corruption free and make the system of blood bank management effective.

The Blood bank system project report contain information related to blood like

- Blood type
- validity of Blood's
- Available Blood group

Need of BloodBank& Donor Management System:

Bank blood donation system in PHP is planned to collect blood from many donators in short from various sources and distribute that blood to needy people who require blood. To do all this we require high quality software to manage those jobs. The government spending lot of money to develop high quality "Blood Bank management system project". For do all those kinds of need blood bank management system project in PHP contain modules which are include the detail of following areas:

- Search Donor
- Become A Donor
- Blood collection
- Blood issued

- Donor Details

1.2:-Objective

The main objective of this application is to automate the complete operations of the blood bank. They need maintain hundreds of thousands of records. Also searching should be very faster so they can find required details instantly.

To develop a web-based portal to facilitate the co-ordination between supply and demand of blood . This system makes conveniently available good quality, safe blood and other blood components, which can be provided in a sound, ethical and acceptable manner, consistent with the long-term well being of the community. It actively encourage voluntary blood donation, motivate and maintain a well-indexed record of blood donors and educate the community on the benefits of blood donation. This will also serve as the site for interaction of best practices in reducing unnecessary utilization of blood and help the state work more efficiently towards self-sufficiency in blood.

The system will provide the user the option to look at the details of the existing Donor List, Blood Group and to add a new Donor. It also allows the user to modify the record. The administrator can alter all the system data.

1.3:-Benefits:

Web-based Blood Donation Management System is a management system website that enables individuals who want to donate blood to help the needy. It also enables hospitals to record and store the data for people who want to communicate with them, and it also provides a centralized blood bank database. The system is developed by using HTML, PHP, and MySQL as a database system to manage and store the data. The Waterfall Methodology, which is the traditional version and the classic approach of a system development life cycle, is used to develop and build the web-based blood bank. The system targets three types of user: the public who wants to donate blood, the recipients who need the donated blood, and the hospitals who that work as an intermediary to manage the communication between the donors and recipients. The main objectives for developing the website is to educate the community on the benefits of blood donation, develop a Web-Based Blood Bank System to manage the records of donors and recipients, and encourage voluntary blood donation, easily accessing any information about blood type and the distribution of the blood in various hospitals in Jeddah, based on the hospital needs.

Our Mission

To endow with strategic and technical expertise to companies wanting to leverage the latest innovations. Our mission is to Define Quality Policy for the IT era, set new span for Services to customers.

1.4:-Minimum Platform Specification:

1.4.1:-Hardware Requirements

- Primary Memory (RAM): 1GB or More.
- Secondary Memory (Hard Disk): 80GB or More.
- Video Display Unit: 15” CRT, or LCD monitor.
- Keyboard: Normal or Multimedia.
- Mouse: Compatible Mouse.

1.4.2:-Software Requirements

- Operating System: Windows XP, 7,8,10.
- Programming Language: PHP 5.6.2
- Markup Language: HTML5
- CSS, Bootstrap, JavaScript
- Database: MySQL.

1.4.3:- Implementation Language

PHP5.6

PHP is an open source scripting language that is widely used to create dynamic website having database connectivity. The name PHP is sort form of “Hypertext Preprocessor” it was initially created by RasmusLerdorf in 1994. He authored the first two versions of PHP. The latest version of php is version 7.2,

PHP5 is 5 to 20 Time faster than java and it is blended with java, c, c++, Perl and c language best feature. PHP can be compiled and optimized to make it run faster by using Zend optimizer that integrated with PHP. It used complete **HTML, CSS, Bootstrap framework, JavaScript.**

Client side scripting:-this type of script is executed on client side browser.

Server side scripting:- this type of script is executed on server side, PHP comes under this category server side scripting interacts with database, fetch the required information specific to the user and display it to the user.

MYSQL:

MySQL is (as of July 2013) the world's second most[a] widely used relational database management system(RDBMS)[9] and most widely used open-source RDBMS.[10] it is named after co-founder Michael Sideniu's daughter, my. [11] .The SQL acronym stands for Structured Query Language. The MySQL development project has made its source code available under the terms of the GNU General Public License, as well as under a variety of proprietary agreements MySQL was owned and sponsored by a single. For-profit firm, the Swedish company MySQL AB, now owned by Oracle Corporation. MySQL is a popular choice of database for use in web application, and is a central component of the widely used LAMP open source web application software stack (and other 'AMP' stacks). LAMP is an acronym for "Linux, Apache, MySQL, Perl/Asp/Python" free-software-open source project that require a full-featured database management system often use MySQL.

HTML5:

HTML stands for Hyper Text Markup Language

HTML describes the structure of Web pages using markup

HTML elements are the building blocks of HTML pages

HTML elements are represented by tags

HTML tags label pieces of content such as "heading", "paragraph", "table", and so on

HTML language is not case sensitive. In this can be use lower and uppercase.

CSS:

CSS Stands for Cascading Style Sheets

CSS describes how HTML elements are to be displayed on screen, paper, or in other media

CSS saves a lot of work. It can control the layout of multiple web pages all at once External style sheets are stored in CSS files

CSS is a style sheet language used for describing the presentation of the document write in markup language.

Bootstrap:

JavaScript is the programming language of html and web.

JavaScript is easy to learn.

JavaScript program them behavior of web page.

It client side scripting language.

SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

Life cycle used ---- **SDLC**

Systems Development Life Cycle (SDLC), or *Software Development Life Cycle*, in systems engineering and software engineering relates to the process of developing systems, and the models and methodologies, that people use to develop these systems, generally computer or information systems.

In software engineering this SDLC concept is developed into all kinds of software development methodologies, the framework that is used to structure, plan, and control the process of dev

Overview

Systems Development Life Cycle (SDLC) is any logical process used by a systems analyst to develop an information system, including requirements, validation, training, and user ownership. An SDLC should result in a high quality system that meets or exceeds customer expectations, within time and cost estimates, works effectively and efficiently in the current and planned Information Technology infrastructure, and is cheap to maintain and cost-effective to enhance.

Computer systems have become more complex and usually (especially with the advent of Service-Oriented Architecture) link multiple traditional systems often supplied by different software vendors. To manage this, a number of system development life cycle (SDLC) models have been created: waterfall, fountain, spiral, build and fix, rapid prototyping, incremental, and synchronize and stabilize. Although in the academic sense, SDLC can be used to refer to various models, SDLC is typically used to refer to a waterfall methodology.

In project management a project has both a life cycle and a "systems development life cycle" during which a number of typical activities occur. The project life cycle (PLC) encompasses all the activities of the project, while the systems development life cycle (SDLC) is focused on accomplishing the product requirements.

FEASIBILITY STUDY

3.1: Technology and system feasibility:

The system requirements i.e. the hardware and software requirements for the project are fulfilled. The hardware and software used for the project are adequate to take inputs from the clients and are giving the desired output on the website which are host in internet the estimated and developed project performs adequately. Website is technically feasible and any system used will be feasible too for the developed project. Website is feasible within the limits of current technology and platform available in web world.

3.2: Economic feasibility:

The project did not cost anything since all the software's were available online and the topics had already been discussed by the faculties and also there were books and tutorials available online for the additional guidance.

3.3: Legal feasibility:

There is no illegal activity occurred in developing this project. All the about the test is correct under their proper term and conditions.

3.4: Operational feasibility:

This website will be developed in fully operational and it also compatible with the technology used in today life. Website can be used in the world wide web of internet. It requires browser to search and used to this site. As it is developed in php, there will be no issue of platform dependency.

LITERATURE SURVEY

4.1 Literature Survey

php5:

PHP: Hypertext Preprocessor (or simply **PHP**) is a server side scripting language designed for web development but also used as a general purpose programming language. It was originally created by Rasmus Lerdorf in 1994, the PHP reference implementation by The PHP Group. PHP originally stood for Personal Home Page, but it now stands for the recursive acronym PHP: Hypertext preprocessor. PHP code may be embedded into HTML code or it can be used in combination with various web template systems, web content management systems, and web frameworks. PHP code is usually processed by a PHP interpreter implemented as a module in the web server or as a Common Gateway Interface (CGI) executable. The web server combines the results of the interpreted and executed PHP code, which may be any type of data, including images, with the generated web page. PHP code may also be executed with a command-line interface (CLI) and can be used to implement standalone graphical applications.

The standard PHP interpreter, powered by the Zend Engine, is free software released under the PHP License. PHP has been widely ported and can be deployed on most web servers on almost every operating system and platform, free of charge.

The PHP language evolved without a written formal specification or standard until 2014, leaving the canonical PHP interpreter as a de facto standard. Since 2014 work has gone on to create a formal PHP specification.

PHP 5 included new features such as improved support for object-oriented programming, the PHP Data Objects (PDO) extension (which defines a lightweight and consistent interface for accessing databases), and numerous performance enhancements. In 2008 PHP 5 became the only stable version under development. Late static binding had been missing from PHP and was added in version 5.

MYSQL:

One great thing about MySQL is that it can be scaled down to support embedded database applications. Perhaps it is because of this reputation that many people believe that MySQL can only handle small to medium-sized systems.

The truth is that MySQL is the de-facto standard database for web sites that support huge volumes of both data and end users (like Friendster, Yahoo, Google). MySQL is a Relational Database Management

System (RDBMS). MySQL AB develops and markets a family of high performance, affordable database servers and tools. Contributing to building the mission-critical, high-volume systems and products worldwide what makes MySQL the world's most popular open source database, as well as its reliability, excellent performance and ease of use. MySQL is not only the world's most popular open source database, it's also the fastest growing database in the industry, with more than 11 million active installations and 50,000 downloads per day

- MySQL is a database server
- MySQL is ideal for both small and large applications
- MySQL supports standard SQL
- MySQL compiles on a number of platforms
- MySQL is free to download and use

HTML with php:

When building a complex page, at some point you will be faced with the need to combine php and HTML to achieve your needed results. At first point, this can seem complicated, since php and HTML are two separate languages, but this is not the case. php is designed to interact with HTML and php scripts can be included in an HTML page without a problem. In an HTML page, php code is enclosed within special php tags. When a visitor opens the page, the server processes the php code and then sends the output (not the Asp code itself) to the visitor's browser. Actually it is quite simple to integrate HTML and php. A php script can be treated as an HTML page, with bits of php inserted here and there. Anything in a php script that is not contained

within<?php?> tags is ignored by the php compiler and passed directly to the web browser. If you look at the example below you can see what a full php script might look like:

Recommended usage:

```
<html>
<head>
<title> this is my page</title>
</head>
<body>
<ul>
<?php for($i=1;$i<=10;$i++) { ?>
<li>list itme<?php $i; ?></li>
<?php } ?>
</ul>
</body>
</html
```

php with MYSQL:

- Knowledge of computer programming.
- php.
- MySQL Connector/NET on your development computer. For more information, [click here](#).
- Knowledge of MySQL and specifically the MySQL.Data Namespace.
- A setup MySQL Database. For more information, see [Creating MySQL or SQL Server Databases for Your Hosting Account](#).

To connect to a MySQL Database Using php

```
<?php
define('_HOST_NAME', 'localhost');
```

```
define('_DATABASE_USER_NAME', 'root');  
  
define('_DATABASE_PASSWORD', '');  
  
define('_DATABASE_NAME', 'mydb');  
  
$MySQLicon=new MySQLi  
(_HOST_NAME,_DATABASE_USER_NAME,_DATABASE_PASSWORD,_DATABASE_NAME);  
if($MySQLicon->connect_errno){  
die('Error in Connection: '.$MySQLicon->connect_error);  
}
```

Php Online:-

As a Website developer, programmer and designer, we all equipped ourselves with local server or Integrated Development Environment installed in our systems for proper execution of code that we write. For this, we need top **best PHP online code compilers** through which we can code something innovative.

There could be a potential situation in which we have a specific code program snippet in our mind but we lack our computer system access to run that code part, then what possibly we can do? We have plenty of web based compiler tools that are online available which can use to execute and run PHP code instead having to download any specific code ignitrons or software extensions for compilation process.

Read more [PHP Web Development services](#)

So, in order to optimize your coding comprehensibility and in time efficient manner you could resort to these best and freely available best PHP compiler online. These compilers are useful for a variety of dynamic purposes like they can speed up the execution of your script since they are no longer interpreted at running time.

Technical Part

4.2 Technology Part

XAMPP

- XAMPP is free and open source and cross-platform web server.
- XAMPP stand for cross-platform apache meriadb php perl.

- Everything need to setup on web server.
- The View displays the data (the database records).
- The Controller handles the input (to the database records).
- The XAMPP also provides full control over HTML, CSS, and JavaScript.

Downloading the Software

- -open online website:- <https://www.apachefriends.org/index.html>
- -click: - XAMPP for window.
- -double click on the download file,
- -click yes when prompted,
- -click next

Front-end & Back-end:

Front End HTML,CSS,Bootstrap:

HTML is a markup language that web browsers use to interpret and compose text, images, and other material into visual or audible web pages. Default characteristics for every item of HTML markup are defined in the browser, and these characteristics can be altered or enhanced by the web page designer's additional use of CSS.

CSS is designed to enable the separation of presentation and content, including layout, colors, and fonts. This separation can improve content accessibility, provide more flexibility and control in the specification of presentation characteristics, enable multiple web pages to share formatting by specifying the relevant CSS in a separate .CSS file, and reduce complexity and repetition in the structural content.

Bootstrap is modular and consists of a series of less style sheets that implement the various components of the toolkit. These style sheets are generally compiled into a bundle and included in web pages, but individual components can be included or removed. Bootstrap provides a number of configuration variables that control things such as color and padding of various components.

Back end is MySQL:

MySQL is a popular choice of database for use in web applications, and is a central component of the widely used LAMP open source web application software stack (and other 'AMP' stacks). LAMP is an

acronym for "Linux, Apache, MySQL, and Perl/PHP/Python." Free-software-open source projects that require a full-featured database management system often use MySQL.

MySQL DataBase

MySQL is a relational database management system (RDBMS) based on SQL (Structured Query Language). First released in January, 1998, MySQL is now one component of parent company MySQL AB's product line of database servers and development tools.

Many Internet startups became interested in the original open source version of MySQL as an alternative to the proprietary database systems from Oracle, IBM, and Informix. MySQL is currently available under two different licensing agreements: free of charge, under the GNU General Public License (GPL) open source system or through subscription to MySQL Network for business applications.

MySQL runs on virtually all platforms, including Linux, UNIX, and Windows. It is fully multi-threaded using kernel threads, and provides application program interfaces (APIs) for many programming languages, including C, C++, Eiffel, Java, Perl, Asp, Python, and TCL(Tool Command Language).

- **Database:** A database is a collection of tables, with related data.
- **Table:** A table is a matrix with data. A table in a database looks like a simple spreadsheet.
- **Column:** One column (data element) contains data of one and the same kind, for example the column postcode.
- **Row:** A row (= tople, entry or record) is a group of related data, for example the data of one subscription.
- **Redondance:** Storing data twice, redundantly to make the system faster.
- **Primary Key:** A primary key is unique. A key value cannot occur twice in one table. With a key, you can find at most one row.
- **Foreign Key:** A foreign key is the linking pin between two tables.
- **Compound Key:** A compound key (composite key) is a key that consists of multiple columns, because one column is not sufficiently unique.
- **Index:** An index in a database resembles an index at the back of a book.
- **Referential Integrity:** Referential Integrity makes sure that a foreign key value always points to an existing row.

Software engineering approach

4.3 Software Engineering approach

Requirement Analysis:

The purpose of the document is to collect and analyze all assorted ideas that have come up to define the system, its requirements with respect to consumers. Also, we shall predict and sort out how we hope this product will be used in order to gain a better understanding of the project, outline concepts that may be developed later, and document ideas that are being considered, but may be discarded as the product develops. In short, the purpose of this SRS document is to provide a detailed overview of our software product, its parameters and goals. This document describes the project's target audience and its user interface, hardware and software requirements. It defines how our client, team and audience see the product and its functionality. Nonetheless, it helps any designer and developer to assist in software delivery lifecycle (SDLC) processes.

System Requirements:

Hardware Requirements

Considering our project, strictly defining hardware requirements is not wise. By the time as our number of users increase, our hardware requirements will not change. As a baseline, we need a single Pentium 4 or above computer with 512 Mb of RAM. Nevertheless, as the number of users increase some enhancements on hardware configurations must be considered:

Moving to a multi-processor and vast memory (both ram and durable storage) server.

Creating clustered server architecture

Software Requirements

Windows or any operating system

Browser.

Internet Connection

Model Used

• Iterative Mode

Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) is extremely vast and full of various development and testing activities, methodologies, techniques, tools, and more. It involves intense planning and management, calculation and preparation. It is only after combining all these efforts of the software engineers that a software or application is successfully developed. Iterative Model is too a part of Software Development Life Cycle. It is a particular implementation of a software development life cycle that focuses on an initial, Diagram of Iterative model:

Figure no.1 Iterative Model

Advantages of Iterative model:

- In iterative model we can only create a high-level design of the application before we actually begin to build the product and define the design solution for the entire product. Later on we can design and build a skeleton version of that, and then evolved the design based on what had been built.
- In iterative model we are building and improving the product step by step. Hence we can track the defects at early stages. This avoids the downward flow of the defects.
- In iterative model we can get the reliable user feedback. When presenting sketches and blueprints of the product to users for their feedback, we are effectively asking them to imagine how the product will work.
- In iterative model less time is spent on documenting and more time is given for designing.

Disadvantages of Iterative model:

- Each phase of an iteration is rigid with no overlaps
- Costly system architecture or design issues may arise because not all requirements are gathered up front for the entire lifecycle

When to use iterative model:

- Requirements of the complete system are clearly defined and understood.
- When the project is big.
- Major requirements must be defined; however, some details can evolve with time

Design**Use Case Diagram:**

The Unified Modeling Language (UML) offers a way to visualize a system's architectural blueprints in a diagram, including elements such as:

- Any activities (jobs)
- Individual components of the system
- And how they can interact with other software components.
- How the system will run
- How entities interact with others (components and interfaces)
- External user interface

Although originally intended solely for object-oriented design documentation, the Unified Modeling Language (UML) has been extended to cover a larger set of design documentation (as listed above),[4] and been found useful in many contexts.

Activity Diagram:

1) User

Figure no.2 Use case diagram (user)

Activity Diagram:

2) Admin

Figure no.3 use case diagram (Admin)

E-R Diagram

4.4 E-R Diagram:

An entity may be defined as a thing capable of an independent existence that can be uniquely identified. An entity is an abstraction from the complexities of a domain. When we speak of an entity, we normally speak of some aspect of the real world that can be distinguished from other aspects of the real world. Paul Beyond-Davies (2004. Database Systems. Hound mills Basingstoke, UK: Palgrave

An entity is a thing that exists either physically or logically. An entity may be a physical object such as a house or a car (they exist physically), an event such as a house sale or a car service, or a concept such as a customer transaction or order (they exist logically—as a concept). Although the term entity is the one most commonly used, following Chen we should really distinguish between an entity and an entity-type. An entity-type is a category. An entity, strictly speaking, is an instance of a given entity-type. There are usually many instances of an entity-type. Because the term entity-type is somewhat cumbersome, most people tend to use the term entity as a synonym for this term.

Entities can be thought of as nouns. Examples: a computer, an employee, a song, a mathematical theorem.

A relationship captures how entities are related to one another. Relationships can be thought of as verbs, linking two or more nouns. Examples: An Owns relationship between a company and a computer, a supervise relationship between an employee and a department; A performs relationship between an artist and a song, a proved relationship between a mathematician and a theorem.

E-R Diagram:

THE COMPLETE ER- DIAGRAM

Figure no.4 ER- Diagram (Entity Relationship Diagram)

Database Design

Table 1: Admin Table

S. no.	Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
1	Id	Integer	Primary key and auto-increment
2	User	Varchar	-
3	Password	Varchar	-
4	Posting Date	Timestamp	-

Table 2: Blood Donors Table

S. no.	Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
1	Id	Integer	Primary key and auto-increment
2	Full Name	Varchar	-
3	Mobile No.	Char	-
4	Email	Varchar	-
5	Gender	Varchar	-
6	Age	Integer	-
7	Blood Group	Varchar	-
8	Address	Varchar	-
9	Message	Mediumtext	-
10	Posting Date	Timestamp	-
11	Status	Integer	-

Table 3: Blood Group Table

S. no.	Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
1	Id	Integer	Primary key and auto-increment
2	Blood group	Varchar	-

3	Posting Date	Timestamp	-
---	--------------	-----------	---

Table 4: Contact Us Info. Table

S. no.	Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
1	Id	Integer	Primary key and auto-increment
2	Address	Tinytext	-
3	Email	Varchar	-
4	Contact No	Char	-

Table 5: Contact Us Query Table

S. no.	Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
1	Id	Integer	Primary key and auto-increment
2	Name	Varchar	-
3	Email Id	Varchar	-
4	Contact No.	Char	-
5	Message	Longtext	-
6	Posting Date	Timestamp	-
7	Status	Int	-

Table 6: Pages Table

S. no.	Field Name	Data Type	Constraints
1	Id	Integer	Primary key and auto-increment
2	Page Name	Varchar	-
3	Type	Varchar	-
4	Detail	Longtext	-

INTRODUCTION OF DFD:-

A DFD, in simple words, is a hierarchical graphical model of a system that shows the different processing activities or functions that the system performs and the data interchange among these functions. In the DFD terminology, it is useful to consider each function as a process that consumes some input data and produces some output data.

The DFD (also known as the bubble chart) is a simple graphical formalism that can be used to represent a system in terms of the input data to the system, various processing carried out on these data, and the output data generated by the system) The main reason why the DFD technique is so popular is probably because of the fact that DFD is a very simple formalism- it is simple to understand and use. A DFD model uses a very limited number of primitive symbols to represent the functions performed by a system and the data flow among these functions. Starting with a set of high-level functions that a system performs, a DFD model hierarchically represents various sub functions. In fact, any hierarchical model is simple to understand. Human mind is such that it can easily understand any hierarchical model of a system-because in a hierarchical model, starting with a very simple and abstract model of a system; different details of the system can be slowly introduced through different hierarchies.

Data flow Diagram:

Figure no.5 Data flow Diagram

SNAPSHOTS

frontend

- **Home**

Figure no.5 Home Page

About Us:

About Us

[Home](#) / [About Us](#)

'BloodBank & Donor Management System' is the first product resulted out of the community welfare initiative called 'People Project' .

Universally, 'Blood' is recognized as the most precious element that sustains life. It saves innumerable lives across the world in a variety of conditions. Once in every 2- seconds, someone, somewhere is desperately in need of blood.

More than 29 million units of blood components are transfused every year. The need for blood is great - on any given day, approximately 39,000 units of Red Blood Cells are needed. Each year, we could meet only up to 1% (approx) of our nation's demand for blood transfusion.

Despite the increase in the number of donors, blood remains in short supply during emergencies, mainly attributed to the lack of information and accessibility. We positively believe this tool can overcome most of these challenges by effectively connecting the blood donors with the blood recipients.

Figure no.7 About Us Page

Why Become Donor:

Why Become Donor

[Home](#) / [Why Become Donor](#)

Safe blood saves lives and improves health. Blood transfusion is needed for:

- women with complications of pregnancy, such as ectopic pregnancies and haemorrhage before, during or after childbirth;
- children with severe anaemia often resulting from malaria or malnutrition;
- people with severe trauma following man-made and natural disasters; and
- many complex medical and surgical procedures and cancer patients.

It is also needed for regular transfusions for people with conditions such as thalassaemia and sickle cell disease and is used to make products such as clotting factors for people with haemophilia.

There is a constant need for regular blood supply because blood can be stored for only a limited time before use.

Regular blood donations by a sufficient number of healthy people are needed to ensure that safe blood will be available whenever and wherever it is needed.

Figure no.8 Why Become Donor Page

Become A Donor:

BloodBank & Donor Management System [About](#) [Why Become Donor](#) [Become a Donor](#) [Search Blood](#) [Contact us](#)

Become a Donor

[Home](#) / [Become a Donor](#)

Full Name* naveen kumar gwala	Mobile Number* 7726906792	Email Id ny772690@gmail.com
Age* 23	Gender* Male	Blood Group* A+
Address panch batti kali paltan tonk RAjasthan	Message* I need blood, its and emergency	

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Figure no.9 Become A Donor Page

Search Donor:

BloodBank & Donor Management System [About](#) [Why Become Donor](#) [Become a Donor](#) [Search Blood](#) [Contact us](#)

Search Donor

[Home](#) / [Search Donor](#)

Blood Group*
AB-

Location
Jaipur

submit

naveen kumar
Mobile No: 7878798787
Email: fkdshfk@gmail.com
Gender : Male
Age: 18
Blood Group : AB

Figure no.10 Search Donor Page

Contact Us:

BloodBank & Donor Management System [About](#) [Why Become Donor](#) [Become a Donor](#) [Search Blood](#) [Contact us](#)

Contact

[Home](#) / [Contact](#)

Send us a Message

Full Name:

Phone Number:

Email Address:

Message:

Contact Details

Demo
P: 7726906792
E: ny772690@gmail.com

Figure no.11 Contact Us Page

Backend:

Admin login:

Figure no. 12 Admin Login Page

Dashboard:

Figure no.13 Dashboard Page

Add Blood Group:

BloodBank & Donor Management System Account ▾

MAIN

- Dashboard
- Blood Group ▾
- Add Donor
- Donor List
- Manage Conatctus Query
- Manage Pages
- Update Contact Info

Add Blood Group

FORM FIELDS

Blood Group

Figure no.14 Add Blood GroupPage

Manage Blood Group:

BloodBank & Donor Management System Account

MAIN

- Dashboard
- Blood Group**
- Add Blood Group
- Manage Blood Group
- Add Donor
- Donor List
- Manage Conatctus Query
- Manage Pages
- Update Contact Info

Manage Blood Groups

LISTED BLOOD GROUPS

Show entries Search:

#	Blood Groups/th>	Creation Date	Action
1	A-	2019-05-12 22:49:32	✕
2	A+	2019-05-12 22:49:45	✕
3	AB-	2019-05-12 22:51:02	✕
4	AB+	2019-05-12 22:51:10	✕
5	O-	2019-05-12 22:51:17	✕

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries PREVIOUS 1 NEXT

Figure no.14 Manage Blood GroupPage

Add Donor:

BloodBank & Donor Management System Account

MAIN

- Dashboard
- Blood Group
- Add Donor
- Donor List
- Manage Conatctus Query
- Manage Pages
- Update Contact Info

Add Donor

BASIC INFO

Full Name*	Ajay verma	Mobile No*	9865589898
Email id	ajayverma@gmail.com	Age*	25
Gender*	Male	Blood Group*	AB+

Address: bada kuwa tonk rajasthan

Message*: i want to donate my blood

Figure no.15 Add Donor Page

Donor List Page:

BloodBank & Donor Management System Account

Donors List

DONORS INFO

[Download Donor List](#)

Show entries Search:

#	Name	Mobile No	Email	Age	Gender	Blood Group	address	Message	action
1	Anuj Kumar	9999857868	anuj@gmail.com	Male	27	O+	bdhdh dhf hd h	d hd hd fh d	Make Hidden Delete
2	dasdasd	41241241241	dasdasd@dfdsf.com	Male	34	AB-	fsdfs	fsdf	Make Hidden Delete
3	rahul kumar	9868958698	rahul123@gmail.com	Male	25	A-	ajmer	love to donate	Make Hidden Delete
4	vinay ajmera	9586987586	ajmera569@gmail.com	Male	25	AB-	tonk	i want to donate	Make Hidden Delete
5	vishakha jain	9568978985	vishakha968@gmail.com	Female	21	O-	jaipur	for donate	Make Hidden Delete
6	rupali agarwal	7759896895	rupalig123@gmail.com	Female	19	A-	jaipur	null	Make Hidden Delete
7	rohan sahu	9895989898	rohan@gmail.om	Male	21	AB+	jaipur	donation	Make Hidden Delete
8	nisha sahu	7798659869	nisha123@gmail.com	Female	21	A+	jaipur	donation	Make Hidden Delete

Figure no.16 Donor List Page

Manage Queries:

BloodBank & Donor Management System

Account

MAIN

- Dashboard
- Blood Group
- Add Donor
- Donor List
- Manage Contactus Query
- Manage Pages
- Update Contact Info

Manage Contact Us Queries

USER QUERIES

Show 10 entries Search:

#	Name	Email	Contact No	Message	Posting date	Action
1	rahul kumar	rahul@gmail.com	9898989898	want to know that how can i become a donor	2019-05-12 21:41:23	Pending Delete

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

PREVIOUS 1 NEXT

7:27 AM 13-May-19

Figure no.16 Manage Queries Page

Manage Pages:

BloodBank & Donor Management System Account

MAIN

- Dashboard
- Blood Group
- Add Donor
- Donor List
- Manage Contactus Query
- Manage Pages**
- Update Contact Info

Manage Pages

FORM FIELDS

select Page

selected Page

Page Details

B / U [Icons] Font Size... Font Family... Font Format... [Icons]

Figure no.17 Manage Pages Page

Update Contact Info:

BloodBank & Donor Management System Account

MAIN

- Dashboard
- Blood Group
- Add Donor
- Donor List
- Manage Contactus Query
- Manage Pages
- Update Contact Info

Update Contact Info

FORM FIELDS

Address	<input type="text" value="demo@demo.com"/>
Email id	<input type="text" value="navengwala@gmail.com"/>
Contact Number	<input type="text" value="7726906792"/>

Figure no.18 Update Contact Info Page

Change Password:

BloodBank & Donor Management System Account ▾

Change Password

FORM FIELDS

Current Password

New Password

Confirm Password

[Save changes](#)

MAIN

- Dashboard
- Blood Group ▾
- Add Donor
- Donor List
- Manage Conatctus Query
- Manage Pages
- Update Contact Info

Figure no.19 Change Password Page

Listed Blood Groups:

BloodBank & Donor Management System Account

MAIN

- Dashboard
- Blood Group**
- Add Donor
- Donor List
- Manage Conatctus Query
- Manage Pages
- Update Contact Info

Manage Blood Groups

LISTED BLOOD GROUPS

Show entries Search:

#	Blood Groups/th>	Creation Date	Action
1	A-	2019-05-12 22:49:32	✕
2	A+	2019-05-12 22:49:45	✕
3	AB-	2019-05-12 22:51:02	✕
4	AB+	2019-05-12 22:51:10	✕
5	O-	2019-05-12 22:51:17	✕
#	Brand Name	Creation Date	Action

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries PREVIOUS **1** NEXT

Donor list-report.xls Show all ✕

Figure no.20 Listed Blood Groups Page

CONCLUSION & FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

This is a website of **BloodBank& Donor Management System**, Where we can find any blood group, Send queries to admin, We can search Any Blood Group and his donor, We can find contact details of the Donor.

In this project we have a separate dashboard where admin can add Blood Group, Manage Blood Group, Add Donor, Manage Contact Us Queries, Manage Pages, Update Contact information.

Admin can Also Remove or Add users and can add new users directly and can easily manage the pages data from the Dashboard.

Future Enhancement

- Website can be extended for other users.
- More areas can be added for Information and help to other.
- Description can be increased.

Bibliography :

- The following books were very helpful during the completion of project
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- Web Enabled Commercial Application Development -Ivan Baryons
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